

CITRATE COMPLEX OF NICKEL

By RABINDRA KUMAR PATNAIK AND S. PANI

Citrate complex of nickel has been investigated by p_H titration method within the p_H range 2.5 to 7. A neutral complex C is formed at lower p_H due to the reaction of a nickel ion and citric acid with the simultaneous liberation of two protons. The equilibrium constant of this reaction has been found to be 7.97×10^{-5} . This complex with increase in p_H dissociates to a H^+ ion and complex C_1^- , the dissociation constant being 1.75×10^{-4} . At still higher p_H the complex C_1^- further dissociates like a monobasic acid to C_2^{2-} and H^+ . The dissociation constant of the latter reaction is 2.35×10^{-8} . The structures of these complexes have been discussed.

Citrate complex of nickel has been studied by Bobbelsky and Joreau (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1945, **67**, 1824) and the existence of a complex containing one citrate ligand per atom of nickel has been reported. The investigation was done in the higher p_H region. The nature of the complex, if any, existing in the lower p_H region appears not to have been investigated. It was therefore thought worthwhile to investigate the problem more thoroughly.

EXPERIMENTAL

The chemicals used were of Analar quality. In the three p_H titrations described below, p_H was measured by a Marconi p_H -meter. Each experiment consists of two p_H titrations and the results are graphically represented by the curve (A) and (B) respectively in Figs. 1-3. Curve (B) represents results obtained with the solution containing a known amount of nickel sulphate, whereas curve (A) represents results obtained in identical condition with the solution containing no nickel sulphate. The details of the experiment are recorded below.

Experiment (I) (Fig. 1).—Curve (A) represents the results of p_H titration of 55 c.c. of a solution containing 0.003 g. mol. of citric acid, and curve (B) that of the same volume of the solution containing 0.003 g. mol. of citric acid and 0.0025 g. mol. of nickel sulphate against N -NaOH at 32.5° .

Experiment (II) (Fig. 2).—Curve (A) represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mol. of potassium nitrate and curve (B) that of the same volume of the solution containing 0.025 g. mol. of nitrate and 0.001 g. mol. of nickel sulphate against $2/3$ neutralised citric acid solution of concentration $0.1M$ at 32° . Potassium nitrate was added to maintain the ionic strength of both the systems very nearly the same.

Experiment (III) (Fig. 3).—Curve (A) represents the results obtained by titrating 100 c.c. of a solution containing 0.025 g. mol. of potassium nitrate, and (B) that of the same volume of the solution containing 0.025 g. mol. of potassium nitrate and 0.00125 g. mol. of nickel sulphate against $0.1M$ sodium citrate solution at 32.5° .

DISCUSSION

The p_n of the system (B) in each case is lower than the corresponding p_n in the system (A). Acid is therefore liberated due to the reaction of nickel ion with citrate ligand and formation of a complex. In Experiment (I: Fig. 1) the horizontal distance between the two curves is the measure of the amount of acid liberated due to the formation of a complex. The horizontal distance at first increases with increasing p_n and then decreases; at about p_n 6, the two curves are very close and the horizontal distance is negligible. This shows that at lower p_n some of the undissociated carboxyl groups of citric acid are induced to ionise due to the formation of a complex with nickel, before the actual p_n for the ionisation of these carboxyl groups is reached. Citric acid in presence of nickel behaves comparatively as a strong tribasic acid.

FIG. 1

No proton is liberated from the hydroxyl group of the citrate ligand due to the formation of the complex, as in such a case citric acid would behave as a tetrabasic acid (in presence of nickel). In Experiment (II: Fig. 2) the p_n of the system containing no nickel is very nearly constant, even with different amounts of two third neutralised citric acid (HCit^{2-} ions). The p_n is, however, low in presence of nickel. This is not due to simple removal of HCit^{2-} ions from the solution by nickel, as this would not change the p_n . This is probably due to the formation of a complex which is a stronger acid than HCit^{2-} . In Experiment (III: Fig. 3) the p_n of the system containing nickel is lower than that of the other system. This is probably due to the removal of citrate ion from the solution by nickel ion. The added citrate ion is

most probably completely removed from the solution and, hence, the p_H does not rise. This complete removal of citrate ion by nickel and formation of an 1:1 complex are indicated by the inflection at about P in curve (B) in Fig 3. The p_H should have

FIG. 2

FIG. 3

increased rapidly after the inflection if no other reaction would have taken place; but the rise in p_H is very gradual. The 1:1 complex formed by the interaction of citrate ligand with nickel is probably an acid and dissociates with increasing p_H .

Calculation of Equilibrium Constant

The reaction taking place in Experiment (I) may be represented by

where C is the nickel citrate complex. The charge of the complex is not shown. The equilibrium constant is given by the equation (1-1) where $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]$, $[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]$, $[\text{C}]$ and $[\text{H}^+]$ represent the molar concentration of nickel ion, citric acid, the complex and hydrogen ion respectively.

$$\frac{[\text{C}] \times [\text{H}^+]^n}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}][\text{H}_3\text{Cit}]} = K \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (1-1)$$

Let A and B be two points on the same p_H axis on curve (A) and (B) respectively in Fig. 1. The reaction taking place at A is the neutralisation of citric acid and formation of dihydrogen citrate ion, monohydrogen citrate ion and citrate ion. At B the complex C is formed besides the neutralisation of citric acid. The molar concentrations of the ions and molecules at A are represented by $[\]_A$ and that at B by $[\]_B$. The p_H being the same, the concentration of the hydrogen ion is represented by $[\text{H}^+]_B$. k_1 , k_2 and k_3 are respectively the first, the second and the third dissociation constant of citric acid ($k_1 = 2.32 \times 10^{-4}$; $k_2 = 4.07 \times 10^{-5}$ and $k_3 = 3.24 \times 10^{-6}$; Schwarzenbach and Ackermann, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1949, 32, 1682). It can be shown

that

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{C}]} = n + \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (2)$$

where,

$$a = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^-]} + 2 \frac{k_1 \times k_2}{[\text{H}^-]^2} + 3 \frac{k_1 \times k_2 \times k_3}{[\text{H}^-]^3} \quad \dots \quad (2-1)$$

$$b = \frac{k_1}{[\text{H}^+]} + \frac{k_1 \times k_2}{[\text{H}^+]^2} + \frac{k_1 \times k_2 \times k_3}{[\text{H}^+]^3} + 1 \quad \dots \quad (2-2)$$

$$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] = [\text{NaOH}]_B - [\text{NaOH}]_A \quad \dots \quad (2-3)$$

$$\Delta[\text{Ct}] = [\text{Ct}]_B - [\text{Ct}]_A \quad \dots \quad (2-4)$$

[Ct] represents the total citrate.

When the formation of the complex is complete $[\text{C}] = [\text{NiSO}_4]$ Hence,

$$\frac{\Delta[\text{NaOH}] - \frac{a}{b} \Delta[\text{Ct}]}{[\text{NiSO}_4]} = n + \frac{a}{b} \quad \dots \quad (3)$$

$[\text{H}^+]$ is obtained from the curve. $[\text{Ct}]_A$, $[\text{NaOH}]_A$, $[\text{Ct}]_B$, $[\text{NaOH}]_B$ and $[\text{NiSO}_4]$ are obtained from the g. mol. of the substance taken or added and the corresponding total volume of the solution (total volume = initial volume + volume of alkali added at A or B). $\Delta[\text{NaOH}]$ and $\Delta[\text{Ct}]$ are calculated, and substituting in equation (3), the value of n is obtained. The value thus calculated are shown in Table I.

TABLE I

pH	a/b	$\Delta[\text{NaOH}] \times 10^2$	$\Delta[\text{Ct}] \times 10^2$	$[\text{NiSO}_4] \times 10^2$	n	$[\text{C}] \times 10^2$	$[\text{H}_3\text{Cit}] \times 10^2$	$[\text{Ni}^{2+}] \times 10^2$	$K \times 10^5$
2.50	0.2131	1.581	0.86	4.432	1.014	0.895	3.492	3.537	7.24
2.60	0.2561	2.082	1.74	4.393	1.090	1.211	3.040	3.182	7.90
2.70	0.3046	2.404	1.32	4.362	1.127	1.442	2.660	2.920	7.39
2.75	0.3311	2.553	1.39	4.340	1.146	1.156	2.468	2.783	7.17
2.80	0.3589	2.710	1.48	4.325	1.170	1.684	2.278	2.641	7.03
2.90	0.4184	3.177	1.74	4.287	1.261	2.053	1.839	2.234	7.92
3.00	0.4826	3.636	2.00	4.251	1.376	2.460	1.417	1.791	6.69
3.10	0.5499	3.767	2.06	4.230	1.430	2.674	1.144	1.556	9.48
3.50	0.8351	5.025	2.74	4.111	2.057	...	...	...	...
3.60	0.9080	5.285	2.89	4.084	2.202	...	...	...	...
3.70	0.9802	5.538	3.02	4.058	2.345	...	...	...	...
3.75	1.016	5.665	3.09	4.044	2.417	...	...	...	...
3.80	1.055	5.642	3.08	4.038	2.450	...	...	...	...
3.90	1.128	5.748	3.15	4.019	2.558	...	...	...	...
4.00	1.203	5.856	3.20	3.999	2.667	...	...	...	...
4.10	1.281	5.817	3.17	3.987	2.740	...	...	...	...
4.20	1.362	5.781	3.16	3.974	2.817	...	...	...	...
4.30	1.445	5.606	3.05	3.968	2.858	...	...	...	...

The value of n is never less than 1. n is < 2 below and > 2 above p_n 3.5. The value of n being < 2 , it is evident that the formation of the complex C is not complete below p_n 3.5. $[C]$ is calculated at $p_n < 3.5$ by equation (2), assuming the value of n to be 2. The concentration of nickel ion is obtained by subtracting $[C]$ from $[\text{NiSO}_4]$. K is calculated by equation (1-1). The values are shown in Table I in the last column. The mean value of K is 7.97×10^{-5} .

Towards the higher p_n range ($n > 2$) more than two protons are liberated. The formation of the complex C is complete and it dissociates like an acid with increasing p_n .

$$\frac{[C_1^-] \times [H^+]}{[C]} = K_1 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4-1)$$

The sum of the concentrations of C and C_1^- would be equal to total nickel.

$$[C] + [C_1^-] = [\text{NiSO}_4] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4-2)$$

Due to the formation C and C_1^- respectively two and three protons would be liberated.

Total acid liberated due to the formation of complex = $2[C] + 3[C_1^-]$. Hence,

$$\frac{2[C] + 3[C_1^-]}{[\text{NiSO}_4]} = n \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4-3)$$

or
$$\frac{[C_1^-]}{[\text{NiSO}_4]} = n - 2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4-4)$$

and
$$\frac{[C]}{[\text{NiSO}_4]} = 3 - n \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (4-5)$$

The value of K_1 can be calculated by substituting $[C_1^-]/[\text{NiSO}_4]$ and $[C]/[\text{NiSO}_4]$ in place of the exact value of $[C_1^-]$ and $[C]$ respectively. The values are recorded in Table II below. The mean value of K_1 is 1.75×10^{-4} .

TABLE II

p_n .	$[C_1^-]/[\text{NiSO}_4]$.	$[C]/[\text{NiSO}_4]$.	$K_1 \times 10^4$.
3.70	0.3480	0.6520	1.65
3.75	0.4170	0.5830	1.27
3.80	0.4500	0.5500	1.29
3.90	0.5380	0.4420	1.59
4.00	0.6670	0.3330	2.00
4.10	0.7400	0.2600	2.26
4.20	0.8170	0.1830	2.82

In Experiment (II) increasing amount of 2/3 neutralised acid is added to a definite amount of nickel sulphate. It is assumed that 2/3 neutralised citric acid mostly consists of HCit^{2-} ion. These ions react with nickel ion affording the complex C.

$$\frac{[C]}{[\text{Ni}^{2+}] \times [\text{HCit}^{2-}]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5-1)$$

The complex C being a stronger acid than HCit^{2-} (dissociation constant of C is 1.75×10^{-4} and that of HCit^{2-} is 3.24×10^{-6}) dissociates according to the reaction (4). As sufficient HCit^{2-} is introduced, the formation of the complex C is complete and dissociation of C to C_1^- and H^+ continues with increasing addition of $2/3$ neutralised citric acid. The equilibrium constants K_1 and K_2 can be calculated from the results of Experiment (II). K_2 differs from K (the equilibrium constant of the reaction of formation of C from nickel ion and citric acid) by a constant and it can be shown that

$$\frac{K}{k_1 \times k_2} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (5-2)$$

The results obtained from this experiment would be more reliable since the ionic strength is very nearly constant and would be a confirmation of the results obtained before.

In the previous experiment with 20% citrate in excess to total nickel, the formation of the complex C is complete at about p_x 3.5. The p_x in this system (curve B, Fig. 2) is always above 3.5. Hence, it is expected that after addition of 20% citrate in excess to the amount of nickel in the solution, the formation of the complex C would be complete. Some nickel ion will be present when the proportion of nickel to citrate in the solution > 1 .

$$\text{Total nickel} = [\text{NiSO}_4] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{Ni}^{2+}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6)$$

When the formation of the complex is complete $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]$ is very small and

$$[\text{NiSO}_4] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6-1)$$

Total citrate = $[\text{Ct}] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] + [\text{Cit}^{3-}]$. The concentration of citric acid would be small and may be neglected. Hence

$$[\text{Ct}] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \times \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + 1 + \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)$$

$$\text{or} \quad [\text{Ct}] = [\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] + a [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6-2)$$

The citrate added to the system is two thirds neutralised (i. e., 2 g. mol. NaOH per g. mol. of citric acid has been added). The amount of acid liberated due to the formation of the complex would be equal to $[\text{C}_1^-]$ which would react with some citrate or monohydrogen citrate ion. If one considers from pure citric acid,

$$\text{Total acid liberated} = 2[\text{C}] + 3[\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{H}_2\text{Cit}^-] + 2[\text{HCit}^{2-}] + 3[\text{Cit}^{3-}]$$

$$\text{Acid neutralised} = 2[\text{Ct}].$$

Hence

$$2[\text{Ct}] + [\text{H}^+] = 2[\text{C}] + 3[\text{C}_1^-] + [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \times \left(\frac{[\text{H}^+]}{k_2} + 2 + 3 \frac{k_3}{[\text{H}^+]} \right)$$

$$\text{or} \quad 2[\text{Ct}] + [\text{H}^+] = 2[\text{C}] + 3[\text{C}_1^-] + b[\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6-3)$$

When the formation of C is complete, the equation (6-2) reduces to

$$[\text{Ct}] = [\text{NiSO}_4] + a [\text{HCit}^{2-}]$$

$$\text{or} \quad [\text{HCit}^{2-}] = \frac{[\text{Ct}] - [\text{NiSO}_4]}{a} \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (6-4)$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ in equation (6-3) and taking $[\text{C}] + [\text{C}_1^-] = [\text{NiSO}_4]$ one gets

$$2[\text{Ct}] + [\text{H}^+] = 2[\text{NiSO}_4] + [\text{C}_1^-] + \frac{b}{a} ([\text{Ct}] - [\text{NiSO}_4])$$

$$\text{or } [\text{Ct}] \times \left(2 - \frac{b}{a}\right) + [\text{H}^+] - [\text{NiSO}_4] \times \left(2 - \frac{b}{a}\right) = [\text{C}_1^-]$$

$$\text{or } ([\text{Ct}] - [\text{NiSO}_4]) \times \left(2 - \frac{b}{a}\right) + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{C}_1^-] \quad \dots \quad (6-5)$$

$[\text{H}^+]$ is obtained from curve (B) in Fig. 2, and a and b are calculated. $[\text{Ct}]$ or $[\text{NiSO}_4]$ is obtained from the g. mol. of two thirds neutralised citric acid added or the g. mol. of nickel sulphate taken and the total volume of the solution. $[\text{C}]$ is obtained by subtracting $[\text{C}_1^-]$ from $[\text{NiSO}_4]$ and K_1 is calculated by equation (4-1). The values are shown in Table III. The mean value 1.945×10^{-4} is in good agreement with the value previously calculated from Experiment (I).

TABLE III

p_{H}	b/a	$[\text{NiSO}_4] \times 10^3$	$[\text{Ct}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{C}_1^-] \times 10^3$	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$K_1 \times 10^4$
3.75	1.192	8.740	1.259	3.289	5.451	1.07
3.80	1.212	8.620	1.379	4.232	4.388	1.53
3.85	1.233	8.517	1.481	4.973	3.544	1.98
3.90	1.255	8.405	1.597	5.758	2.647	2.74
3.95	1.279	8.307	1.694	6.334	1.973	3.60

The mean value of $K_1 = 1.94 \times 10^{-4}$.

For the range in which proportion of nickel to citrate is >1 , the calculation can be made as follows :

$$[\text{C}] = \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1} [\text{C}_1^-].$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{C}]$ in equation (6-2) and (6-3), one gets

$$[\text{Ct}] = [\text{C}_1^-] \times \left(1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1}\right) + a [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (7)$$

and

$$2[\text{Ct}] + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{C}_1^-] \times \left(3 + 2 \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1}\right) + b [\text{HCit}^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (7-1)$$

Substituting the value of $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ from equation (7), the equation (7-1) reduces to

$$2[\text{Ct}] + [\text{H}^+] = [\text{C}_1^-] \times \left(3 + \frac{2[\text{H}^+]}{K_1}\right) + \frac{b}{a} \left\{ [\text{Ct}] - [\text{C}_1^-] \times \left(1 + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1}\right) \right\}$$

$$\text{or } \frac{[\text{Ct}] \times \left(2 - \frac{b}{a}\right) + [\text{H}^+]}{\left(3 - \frac{b}{a}\right) + \frac{[\text{H}^+]}{K_1} \left(2 - \frac{b}{a}\right)} = [\text{C}_1^-] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (7-2)$$

All the quantities in equation (7-2) except $[\text{C}_1^-]$ are known. $[\text{C}_1^-]$ is calculated at different p_{H} values and C by equation (4-1), substituting the values of $[\text{C}_1^-]$ and K_1 . $[\text{Ni}^{2+}]$ is obtained by subtracting the sum of the concentrations of C and C_1^- from $[\text{NiSO}_4]$. $[\text{HCit}^{2-}]$ is calculated from equation (7-1). The values of K_2 , thus calculated, are shown in Table IV. The values are fairly constant.

TABLE IV

p_{H}	b/a	$[\text{Ct}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{NiSO}_4] \times 10^3$	$[\text{C}_1^-] \times 10^3$	$[\text{C}] \times 10^3$	$[\text{HCit}^{2-}] \times 10^4$	$[\text{Ni}^{2+}] \times 10^3$	$K_1 \times 10^{-3}$	$K \times 10^5$
3.64	1.155	0.9902	9.902	0.3753	0.4421	0.2594	9.085	1.876	6.352
3.58	1.137	1.961	9.804	0.6452	0.8726	0.5929	8.286	1.776	6.015
3.56	1.132	2.913	9.709	0.9374	1.327	0.7202	7.447	2.475	8.379
3.57	1.134	5.661	9.434	1.688	2.335	2.150	5.411	2.007	6.797
3.58	1.137	6.542	9.346	1.950	2.637	2.612	4.759	2.121	7.185
3.59	1.140	7.408	9.260	2.210	2.920	3.113	4.130	2.272	7.691
3.62	1.145	8.256	9.175	2.509	3.095	3.832	3.571	2.261	7.658
3.63	1.152	9.090	9.090	2.745	3.309	4.550	3.036	2.395	8.110

The values of K , calculated from the corresponding values of K_2 according to the equation (5-2) are in agreement with those calculated from the results of Experiment (I). The mean value is 7.53×10^{-5} .

In Experiment (III) (Fig. 3) the complex C_1^- is formed with increasing addition of sodium citrate as the p_{H} is high. The complex is a very stable one and the formation is very nearly complete when 1 g. mol. of sodium citrate is added per g. atom of nickel. On further addition of sodium citrate, the p_{H} , as expected, does not rise rapidly. It is very probable that complex C_1^- dissociates like a monobasic acid as the p_{H} is increased by increasing addition of sodium citrate. The reaction may be represented by equation (8). The proton thus liberated, is partly consumed by the citrate ion.

$$\frac{[\text{C}_2^{2-}] \times [\text{H}^+]}{[\text{C}_1^-]} = K_2 \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (8-1)$$

Total citrate = $[\text{Ct}] = \text{free citrate} + \text{citrate in the complex.}$

Free citrate = $[Ct^{3-}] + [HCit^{2-}] + [H_2Cit^{-}] + [H_3Cit]$.

The concentration of citric acid would be small and may be neglected. Hence

$$\text{Free citrate} = [HCit^{2-}] \times \left(\frac{k_3}{[H^+]} + 1 + \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} \right) = a [HCit^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad (9)$$

$$\text{Citrate in the complex} = [C_1^-] + [C_2^{2-}] = [NiSO_4] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-1)$$

Hence

$$[Ct] - [NiSO_4] = a [HCit^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-2)$$

The amount of acid liberated = $[C_2^{2-}]$.

The amount of acid consumed = $[HCit^{2-}] + 2[H_2Cit^{-}]$

$$= [HCit^{2-}] \times \left(1 + 2 \frac{[H^+]}{k_2} \right) = b [HCit^{2-}].$$

Hence

$$[C_2^{2-}] = [H^+] + b [HCit^{2-}] \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-3)$$

Substituting the value of $[HCit^{2-}]$ from equation (9-2), the above equation is reduced to

$$[C_2^{2-}] = [H^+] + \frac{b}{a} ([Ct] - [NiSO_4]) \quad \dots \quad \dots \quad (9-4)$$

$[H^+]$ is obtained from curve (B) in Fig. 3 and $a, b, [Ct]$ and $[NiSO_4]$ are calculated as before. $[C_2^{2-}]$ is calculated by equation (9-4). $[C_1^-]$ is obtained by subtracting $[C_2^{2-}]$ from $[NiSO_4]$. K_3 is calculated by equation (8-1). The results are recorded in Table V. The mean value of K_3 is 1.35×10^{-8} .

TABLE V

pH .	$[NiSO_4]$.	$[Ct]$.	b/a .	$[C_2^{2-}] \times 10^4$.	$[C_1^-] \times 10^3$.	$K_3 \times 10^8$.
6.2	0.01092	0.01259	0.1676	2.799	1.064	1.660
6.3	0.01085	0.01319	0.1371	3.207	1.053	1.530
6.4	0.01074	0.01409	0.1115	3.736	1.037	1.430
6.5	0.01064	0.01482	0.0903	3.775	1.026	1.160
6.6	0.01052	0.01582	0.0728	3.857	1.024	0.955

Structure of the Complex

In the Experiment (I) it is observed that n is never < 1 . In the formation of the complex C two of the three carboxyl groups of citric acid are attached. It is, however, difficult to predict which of the two carboxyl groups take part in the reaction. For the formation of a stable complex, the formation of five- or six-membered ring is necessary. Hence, the hydroxyl group of citric acid most probably forms a co-ordinate bond with nickel. The complex is expected to be a four co-ordination one. Since the citrate ligand can occupy only three co-ordination position, the fourth co-ordination position is occupied by a molecule of water. There is, however, certain justification in assuming this. The complex is an aquo-complex, the water molecule of which ionises at about neutral point furnishing the hydroxo-complex. The structures may be represented as follows :

(Complex C)

[Complex C₂²⁻].

If the proton is liberated from the hydroxyl group joined to the nickel atom in complex C but not from water molecule as suggested above, the complex C may be represented by structures shown below.

The authors are thankful to the Board of Scientific and Industrial Research for awarding a grant for chemicals and apparatus. Sri R.K. Patnaik, the junior author, is thankful to the Utkal University for awarding him a scholarship so as to enable him to take part in this investigation.